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ETHICAL DECISION MAKING IN EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS: EXPLORING THE VIEWS OF MANAGERS IN PRIVATE LIFELONG LEARNING CENTERS IN PATRAS, GREECE

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Abstract

This research focuses on investigating the opinions of managers in private lifelong learning centers in Patras, Greece, regarding ethical decision-making in educational organizations. More specifically, it focuses on the connection between the ethical values of education and private educational organizations, as well as how to ensure ethical decisions and understand the importance of the ethical decision-making process for a lifelong learning center. For an in-depth understanding of the opinions, the qualitative methodological approach was chosen, and the semi-structured interview was used as a research tool. The sample of the research consists of 12 managers, who are responsible for the design, implementation, and evaluation of the professional training projects. Findings from the data analysis showed that the field of education and private educational organizations share common ethical values. For Lifelong Learning Centers in particular, ensuring ethical decision-making is a function of many factors that play a prominent role in maintaining, developing, and strengthening interpersonal relationships within the organization. Ultimately, the process of making ethical decisions promotes the longevity of the organization by building a map of orientation towards its purpose and goals.

Keywords: ethics, decision-making, educational organization, lifelong learning center, management

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Introduction

Theorists of ethical philosophy brought ethics to the fore as a factor in social cohesion and well-being. Ethics is a particularly malleable concept because of its ability to evolve according to the reference context. It can also be carefully reflected through decision-making (Chakrabarti & Chatterjea, 2020; Poatsy, 2011). Decision-making is a complex and demanding process where positive intentions are not enough to achieve the desired result (Poatsy, 2011; Hoffrage, 2011). Particularly in the microcosm of modern organizations, this complexity is maximized and depends on many factors, one of which is ethical behavior. When it comes to educational organizations, the decision-making process has an impact on the social context and is based on ethical values such as honesty, respect, and fairness (Evin, 2007). Educational organizations with a focus on lifelong learning cultivate these values to guide personal development. In this case, management takes on a different approach, and ethical decision-making is oriented towards pedagogical values (Oliver & Hioco, 2012). As for managers, they are responsible for leading on the right moral path (Al Halbusi et al., 2021).

This research aims to examine the ethical decision-making process in lifelong learning centers. More specifically, it seeks the role of ethical values as well as the assurance and importance of the process for both the organization and the managers. The problematic issue and the stimulus for delving deeper into this issue was the dissatisfaction that was observed from the large volume of responsibilities that lifelong learning centers had to manage. That dissatisfaction began to raise questions of moral loyalty. This particular educational problem is an aspect of the social question of whether we understand that an ethical decision depends solely on the individual or needs to be contextualized. The literature review, through the approach of the concepts of ethics, ethical behavior, and the link between decision-making and educational context, builds the background for the research methodology. After that, the stages and the results of the research are described in detail, and finally, the conclusions are formulated.

Literature Review

Role of ethics and ethical behavior

One of the basic questions that has occupied human thought and continues to be at the forefront to this day concerns the characterization of a human action as good or bad. Ethics, as one of

the basic branches of philosophy, attempts to answer that question (Neiman, 2004). This attempt is not as simple as it may sound. The clarification of the term followed a progressive development that highlighted how it needs to be approached. The first references come from ancient Greece and continue with its association with natural disasters and divine signs as a consequence of the fall of man. With the changes in the socio-political context, ethics became linked to the power of reasoning and the principles on which the individual makes decisions. Eventually, after World War II, the focus shifted to the context, which gives meaning to the actions and decisions (Hartman, DesJardins, & MacDonald, 2021; Chakrabarti & Chatterjea, 2020). This brings back the initial difficulty in approaching ethics, as it is often determined by factors that are not always recognized (Bazerman & Tenbrunsel, 2011).

For organizations, the study of ethics is important as it shapes a work environment with positive interactions, active engagement, and a sense of mutual respect (Chakrabarti & Chatterjea, 2020). But even in this case, ensuring an ethical culture is a challenge. Ethical behavior depends on the ethical culture, which refers to the way the organization communicates its values. When an organization is characterized by a strong ethical culture, it directs its people to be alert and vigilant. This factor shapes ethical behavior and influences the decision-making process (Bazerman & Tenbrunsel, 2011; Schwartz, 2017). The problem is that managerial and executive positions are often characterized by risk in decision-making, ignoring potential ethical risks (Poatsy, 2011).

Ethical decision-making and management

An understanding of ethics is a key prerequisite for an approach to ethical decision-making. To date, a sufficient number of theoretical models have been formulated in order to approach the ethical decision-making process. However, there is no agreement from the entire scientific community as to which one is the most appropriate, so the need to deepen the theory is timely. There are many factors that determine ethical decision-making, such as organizational values, the influence of social institutions, and the importance of the issue (Schwartz, 2017). This interest demonstrates how important ethical management is for the organizational environment. It is a response to fulfill social responsibility in order to communicate the ethical values of the organization with the social context (Snellman, 2015). Apart from that, such a strategy reinforces the ethical culture

(Al Halbusi et al., 2021). The manager is responsible for executing this strategy and needs to be well trained. After all, his moral direction shapes the behavior of his coworkers (Snellman, 2015).

For educational organizations, exploring ethical decision-making is important because it helps harmonize different goals, for example, social, educational, or economic. It acts as a compass to help them set priorities (Maesschalck, 2004). In addition, the ethical guidelines promote, as stated, the social responsibility of the organization. That is, it does not neglect to enhance social welfare. Finally, decisions with an ethical orientation incorporate pedagogical values and give priority to the respect of students (Oliver & Hioco, 2012).

Ethical Dimension in Educational Organizations

For educational organizations, management is equally challenging and complex (Katsaros, 2008). The manager needs to have very good knowledge of the target group he or she is addressing, as well as of the educational news. At the same time, they are required to identify and accurately manage the educational objectives. These are some of the particular characteristics of educational organizations. So, in this context, there is often confusion in decision-making. This is where ethical issues may come into play (Cranston et al., 2006). The emphasis on the ethical decision-making process in education is due to the fact that decisions are mirrored in society. They are also based on democratic principles and represent the ethical values of education. The ethical decision-making process for educational organizations ensures not only sustainability but also a good reputation and confidence in the quality-of-service delivery (Hrestic, Popescu, & Panagoret 2015).

In the case of a lifelong learning center, the ethical decision-making process is promoted and adapted to its own particular characteristics and to external conditions. In Greece, the educational system is centralized, meaning that educational organizations are not flexible and educational planning is hampered by bureaucracy (Bouzakis, 2002; Katsaros, 2008). A lifelong learning center is a distinct category of educational organization that functions as an institution for adult training. It is found in both the public and private sectors. Its function is defined by the law, which ensures a minimum level of ethical compliance, and as a result, the ethical approach to decisions attracts great interest (Menzel, 2007). Approaching lifelong learning from an ethical perspective, the aim is to promote moral values in the

educational process in order to achieve character development (Najder-Stefaniak, 2013). Through the search and study of the literature, it was observed that ethical decision-making in lifelong learning centers has not come to the forefront of research. The connection between ethics and education has been addressed mainly through the study of ethical leadership in schools and conflict management (Göçen, 2021; Pappa, 2018; Konti, 2021).

Methodology

Aim and Research Questions

The main purpose of this research is to explore and understand the views of managers in private lifelong learning centers in the City of Patras, Greece, regarding ethical decision-making in educational organizations. Specifically, the sub-objectives of the research include: 1) the search for the connection between the ethical values of education and private educational organizations. 2) the way to ensure ethical decision-making, and 3) the importance of this process for the organization.

Consequently, the research questions posed, as adapted and restated in the progress of the study, are the following:

What is the connection between education and private educational organizations in terms of ethical values?

How is it ensured that an ethical decision is made in a lifelong learning center?

Why is the ethical decision-making process important in a lifelong learning center?

Methodological Approach

The methodological approach that was used for this research was qualitative methodology. The main reason for this choice is to explore the phenomenon in depth in order to gain a detailed understanding of the various aspects. Qualitative research makes an important contribution when the researcher comes into contact with issues that have not been adequately explored (Isari & Pourkos, 2015). As the literature search revealed, the ethical decision-making process in lifelong learning centers in the Patras region has not been the subject of previous research. At the same time, the ethical approach emphasizes the context, as does the qualitative methodology (Bazerman & Tenbrunsel, 2011). Ethics is a vague research subject in which it is difficult to measure moral actions and behaviors (Snellman, 2015).

Sample Selection

The sample of the present research consists of twelve managers in private lifelong learning centers in the Municipality of Patras, namely eight women and four men. Purposive sampling was chosen in order for the sample to best respond to the purpose and questions of the research.

Research tool

The semi-structured interview was used as a research tool because of the flexibility it offers. The aim is to access the complexity of human behavior. The researcher lists a number of questions that cover the main points of the research. The axes are predefined, but flexibility is provided as it is possible to skip, add, or deepen the questions at the time of the survey. Based on the research questions, three research axes and thirteen questions were formed. These were formulated after studying the relevant literature and adapted during the research. Questions 1 and 6 come from the study of Evin's (2007) article, which argues for the promotion of ethical management goals in education. Based on chapters 1 to 3 in Schwartz's (2017), regarding the process and barriers of the decision-making process, questions 2, 7, 9, 10, and 12 were derived. Then questions 3 and 4 were based on the article Najder-Stefaniak (2013), which analyzes the ethical dimension in the design and organization of lifelong learning. In the book by Ferrell, Fraedrich, & Ferrell (2019) regarding the contribution of ethical climate within organizations, in chapter eight, question 5 was formulated. Menzel's (2005) article on the ethical extension of public administration and policy formed the basis for question 8. Finally, question 11 was based on Oliver & Hioco's (2012) article on the supportive framework for the management of educational organizations in conjunction with ethical decision-making, and question 13 was based on the article by Hrestic, Popescu, & Panagoreț (2015) on improving management in education from an ethical perspective.

The three axes under which the questions were created are the following:

- A. Views of the managers of lifelong learning centers (in Patras) on the link between the ethical values of education and private educational organizations.
- B. Managers' views on how to ensure that an ethical decision is made in a lifelong learning center

C. Views on the importance of the ethical decision-making process in their organization.

The following are the detailed questions in the interview guide:

- 1) The field of education is characterized by certain ethical principles. What are they, in your opinion?
- 2) In your opinion, does the nature of the organization, as an educator, have an influence on its ethical profile?
- 3) What are the ethical values that accompany an educational organization? Do they coincide with those that were mentioned for the education sector?
- 4) In your opinion, are there cases where the educational organization deviates from the moral ideals of education?
- 5) What do you consider to be your role in shaping the ethical climate of the organization?
- 6) What influences do you think your organization receives from the Ministry of Education in terms of ethical direction?
- 7) How do you assess whether a decision you have made for the organization is ethical?
- 8) Do you take steps to ensure ethical orientation throughout your organization?
- 9) What do you think are the biggest challenges for you to ensure ethics in your organization?
- 10) In your opinion, what characteristics does a manager need to have in order to make ethical decisions?
- 11) As far as your organization is concerned, do you think it is important for the decision-making process to follow and take into account ethical parameters?
- 12) What would you suggest in order to strengthen the decision-making process?
- 13) What benefit could this process have in the long run for the organization?

Questions 1 to 4 correspond to the first axis, questions 5 to 10 to the second axis, and finally, questions 11 to 13 to the third axis. At the beginning, questions were asked in order to get to know the interviewee and collect demographic data.

Data collection procedure and analysis

Data collection was carried out from November 2022 to January 2023. A list from the Ministry of Education for the years 2022–2023 was used in order to detect private lifelong learning centers in the Municipality of Patra. Via email, managers were invited to participate

in the survey and were informed about the purposes, the interview process, the available timeframe, the protection of personal data, and the audio recording. Prior to conducting the interviews, a pilot interview was conducted in order to obtain feedback on the suitability and possible adjustments of the questions. The interviews were conducted in person at the offices of each center. They lasted an average of 25 minutes and were followed by a transcription process.

For the analysis of the data, a thematic analysis was chosen, which involves the identification, formation, and description of "recurrent mental patterns" from the interview data while also significantly contributing to familiarizing new researchers with the qualitative methodology (Isari & Pourkos, 2015). The research questions guide the process of analysis, and the literature review serves as a frame of reference for the data coding stage. The process includes the stages of transcription, coding the interview, and creating the themes. In more detail, after the whole interview is coded, by merging and contrasting the codes, the themes and their specific features emerge. They are general categories that constitute the interpretation and in-depth exploration of the interviewees' opinions. It evolves dynamically and not in a linear way, as it requires the active involvement of the researcher (Tsiolis, 2018).

Safeguarding scientific ethics and principles

The research process is meaningful if the participants are effectively protected. Research ethics is a complex process, especially with qualitative approaches, because of its flexibility, lack of predictability, and the direct contact of the researcher with the participants (Isari & Pourkos, 2015). Particular emphasis was given as the involvement of ethics was a concern from the beginning due to issues of sensitivity and discretion that may arise. Participants were made aware of the purpose and objectives of the study, given a consent form, and were not addressed with personal or guided questions.

As far as the validity of the research is concerned, this is achieved by the detailed description at each stage of the research method, the consistency of the steps of the methodology, and the adherence to ethics. As for the research tool, in order to ensure validity, the required ethics regarding anonymity and confidentiality were respected, and an effort was made to create a pleasant and calm atmosphere that promotes trust in the interviewees. The preparation of the questions and the selection of the time and place according to

their availability had been done beforehand. On the other hand, reliability is achieved by accurately stating the reasons for the choice of methods at each stage, as was done for the sample and the interview (Isari & Pourkos, 2015). For the interview tool in particular, it is enhanced by ensuring that the researcher is not biased towards the interviewees. At the same time, in this particular investigation, there was no personal relationship between the researcher and the interviewees. The validity of qualitative research ultimately rests on the detailed description and honest presentation of the whole context and «the history of the research itself' alongside the stories of the participants» (Mulholland & Wallace, 2003).

Discussion of the findings

In this chapter, the analysis of the empirical material resulting from the transcription of the interviews is carried out, starting with the demographic data as presented in the first table. Secondly, the analysis of the data is carried out for each question per axis separately.

Interviewees	Gender	Education	Age	Years of experience
A Interviewee	Woman	Master degree	57+	17
B Interviewee	Woman	Master degree	38-47	20
C Interviewee	Woman	Bachelor	38-47	3
D Interviewee	Woman	Bachelor	27-37	3
E Interviewee	Man	Bachelor	48-57	12
F Interviewee	Woman	Master degree	27-37	6
G Interviewee	Man	Bachelor	57+	20
H Interviewee	Man	Master degree	27-37	2
I Interviewee	Man	Master degree	38-47	9

J Interviewee	Woman	Master degree	38-47	7
K Interviewee	Woman	Master degree	27-37	6
L Interviewee	Woman	Master degree	27-37	7

Table 1. Demographic features of participants

The sample consists of twelve managers of private lifelong learning centers in the municipality of Patras, of which four are men and eight are women. An equal distribution of participants was sought, but, as it turned out, in the study area, women were more represented in this particular position. Regarding the educational level, the majority of participants have a Master's degree diploma, belong to the age group 27–37, and have less than ten years of experience in a managerial position as a manager in a private lifelong learning center. Based on the interviewees' responses, it is worth noting that none of them stated that they had received training in ethical management.

Following, the results of the thematic analysis are presented, using a thematic map for each research question and axis. At the top of the map is the research question, so there is a picture of what is being searched for each time. The second row presents, from left to right, the main themes that emerged for each of the questions in the axis. The third row illustrates the detailed features of each theme.

What is the connection between education and private educational organizations in terms of ethical values?

Figure 1. The link between the ethical values of education and private educational organizations

The analysis of the empirical data in the first axis highlighted that managers recognize that education is mainly linked to moral values such as fairness and respect. Ethics is differentiated and distinguished in educational organizations as it focuses on the human being and its cultivation. This is accomplished by giving priority to the support and ethical development of students. At the same time, ethical values for private lifelong learning centers (such as integrity and fairness) were recorded, which, as the managers pointed out, coincide to a large extent with those of the education sector. In this way, a common ethical core is drawn together. Particular importance is attached to the fact that commitment to ethical values ensures students' trust and shapes them for tomorrow's society. In this context, educators are the representatives of ethics. However, it is evident that maintaining the common ethical core is not an easy task, as in cases where economic interests prevail, the educational organization loses its orientation.

How is it ensured that an ethical decision is made in a lifelong learning center?

Figure 2. Ensuring ethical decision-making in the lifelong learning center

Continuing with the second research question, the interest centers on how to ensure that an ethical decision is made for the lifelong learning center. The thematic map includes the six questions on the second axis. The analysis of the data indicated that the manager is involved in building the ethics of the organization in two ways: by strengthening interpersonal relationships and by the way he or she promotes and communicates his or her ethical values. In decision-making as a whole, managers perceive their contribution to shaping the ethical culture as crucial. Further, the ethical influence of government institutions in decision-making was investigated. It emerged that the attitude of the Ministry of Education is limited to promoting a strict legal framework where ethical guidance is not distinct. It is questioned as communication with the Ministry is a source of stress and confusion. The very next question dealt with how the manager evaluates their decisions as ethical. For them, evaluation is something subjective and depends on the individual's priorities. As a measure to ensure ethical decision-making, interviewees considered the most important investment to be the development of interpersonal relationships. In this way, the decision-making process takes place in a fertile environment. Of course, in order to illustrate the way ethical decisions are made in the lifelong learning center, it is appropriate to identify, in the opposite direction, the obstacles that undermine them as unethical. The biggest ethical

challenge is financial management, as the organization is under pressure both from within (senior managers) and from outside (the Ministry of Education) to make quick and effective decisions. Finally, the manager's characteristics that contribute to ethical decision-making are listed. The greatest emphasis was placed on the ethical profile of the manager, highlighting ethical values such as temperance, justice, respect, honesty, integrity, and dignity. In this way, the common interest is served.

Why is the ethical decision-making process important in a lifelong learning center?

Figure 3. Importance of ethical decision-making process in the lifelong learning center

The third and last axis brings the research question directly to the forefront from the very beginning. It consists of three questions. Here, managers were asked to express their opinion on the importance of the ethical decision-making process for the lifelong learning center. With the exception of one interviewee, all the others acknowledge that it is a compass to guide them in order to prevent mistakes and conflicts. The ethical decision-making process can be strengthened and improved by promoting cooperation and team spirit, thus building a relationship of trust that involves both members and students. The discussion of the findings concludes with the question of the long-term benefit of the ethical decision-making process for the lifelong learning center. The biggest benefit

highlighted was the good reputation gained by the educational organization. This is linked both to the satisfaction of the students and to its outward-looking nature towards the local community. In other words, the ethical decision-making process does not simply contribute to survival.

Conclusions

This research was transferred to an organizational environment where the ethical element is both dynamic and evolving. Lifelong Learning Centers, as organizations for adult education, promote ethical decision-making by adapting it to their own particular characteristics and external circumstances. The purpose of the research was to investigate the views of managers and to try to identify what place the ethical decision-making process ultimately occupies in the lifelong learning center in Patras, Greece. In many points, for example, as a measure for making an ethical decision or as a means of strengthening the process, the strengthening of interpersonal relations was highlighted. Investing in the human factor is therefore of paramount importance. With such a measure to ensure ethics, the decision-making process is on fertile ground. On the other hand, economic interests are often an obstacle to the ethical decision-making process and commitment to moral values. After all, the lifelong learning center, as a private educational organization, remains partly captive to profit. Overall, the way in which ethical decision-making is ensured is a function of several factors. The literature raises several questions about how it is achieved, as it is a complex process. That is why in the second axis, questions were formed to explore the role of the manager, the ministry, the way of evaluation, and the challenges in order to cover this context as best as possible. For the manager in particular, the responsibility for shaping the ethical culture is recognized. The commitment to promote the ethical decision-making process is primarily an organizational choice. As demonstrated, the Greek Ministry of Education lacks a dynamic presence and a meaningful role in moral leadership. Thus, the request for an ethical approach to lifelong learning centers was expressed. Against cases of ethical disorientation, the ethical values of education provide a safety net and a strong support for the ethical compliance of the organization. Finally, it is worth noting where some managers sought their answers outside the organizational context and linked ethics to the social context. In this way, a horizon of concern opens up to the sociology of education as questions are raised about the social role of

educational organizations. Through this study, useful information about the ethical culture of a lifelong learning center was obtained. When approaching the concept of business, customer service does not disappear from the foreground. However, the ethical values of education combined with social responsibility seem to be a protective shield against ethical disorientation. This double role is reflected in the decision-making process, as particular emphasis was placed by managers on the development and strengthening of interpersonal relationships.

The difficulty of comparison with similar surveys opens up the discussion of the limitations presented. However, it attempts to raise research interest and open up the scientific debate for further exploration of ethics in education. Furthermore, due to the nature of the research being qualitative, it only focuses on the dimensions that the participants themselves choose to disclose, with the possibility of withholding critical or non-critical information about the particular issue. At the same time, due to the small sample size and representation of men in the survey, it is not possible to draw safe connections with demographic data. The problematic aspects of the process of ethical decision-making can be advanced by broadening the research. The following are suggested as indicative research topics for future work on the subject: a more in-depth comparison between business and private educational organizations in relation to ethics; the process of ethical decision-making in schools with teachers or principals as participants; ethical dilemmas in the field of education; the ethical and non-ethical behavior in the modern educational system; and the contribution of the behavior of students. Education officials and all relevant stakeholders are critical to understanding the momentous role of ethical education for active citizens. After all, education is a refuge for ethics, as an educational system shapes the perception and values of society (Parson, 2016).

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